

MEd: Education & Professional Development

Dissertation

Envisaging ‘Nothing about us, without us’

Exploring the perspectives of SEND learners and teachers on the integration of SEND learners into mainstream educational settings.

Dean Graham, May 2025

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1. Introduction

This research project aims to explore the perspectives of Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (SEND) learners and teachers on the idea of integrating SEND learners into mainstream educational settings. This project was designed to conduct research with SEND learners and their educational practitioners, as opposed to gaining the perspectives of other stakeholders which includes parents, local authorities and the UK government on the matter. By researching the perspectives of SEND learners on the idea of integrating them into mainstream provisions, this research was able to draw qualitative data from those with a diagnosis of SEND and allows their voice to be amplified on a topic that is imperative in their education and development. In addition, this research project crucially explores the perspectives of teachers who work with SEND learners in specialist provisions, this research offers insight into the complexity of adapting and supporting the diverse needs of SEND learners in education which are generally misunderstood in terms of practicality versus theory.

The topic of this research was chosen to probe discussion among relevant stakeholders in SEND education who collectively work towards achieving the *United Nations'* (2022) sustainable development goal to 'ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all by 2030.' The notion of 'inclusion' in this goal is interpreted as 'integration' by the researcher.

This project aims to offer qualitative data on the following questions:

- 1. How do SEND learners view the idea of being integrated into mainstream educational settings, and what are their feelings around this?**
- 2. What is the perception of teachers working in SEND education around the possible integration of SEND learners into mainstream settings?**

This project will focus on the perspectives of SEND learners between the ages of 18-24 years old with an Educational Health Care Plan (EHCP) in place, and who attend Further Education (FE) specialist provisions as their diverse needs cannot be met in mainstream FE provisions. It will also gain the perspectives of SEND practitioners who have extensive experience working in SEND (FE) education.

The process of this research from the design to the dissemination was conducted over a duration of 8 months (September 2024 – April 2025) in Northern England. The project involved conducting semi-structured interviews with five SEND learners in a specialist FE provision who were working on courses as part of a 'Preparing for Adulthood (PFA)' curriculum which focuses on areas such as independent living, health and wellbeing, friends, relationships and the community, and life and employment skills. As part of the course, learners also had the opportunity to explore their hobbies and interests and gain new skills and knowledge in a range of vocational areas whilst working towards completing entry-level and/or functional skills qualifications in Maths, English and ICT. In addition, questionnaires were designed and disseminated via Google Forms to five SEND teachers within the same provision, of which three submitted their responses to the questions posed in the form.

There are limitations that are associated with this research, one of which is that it is a small-scale project and therefore does not aim to offer a conclusion to the questions listed above but does offer opportunity in the sense that this could be explored further to a much larger scale. As this research project uses a small sample from the same educational provision, this may not reflect the experiences and perspectives of others outside of the study context. There is also a potential for researcher bias due to my personal experience, knowledge and presence within SEND education which may influence my interpretation, which increases the risk of subjective bias. This may impact the reliability and credibility of the findings.

This paper has been structured in a format that will allow the reader to gain a clear understanding of the research that has been conducted. The rationale of the project will provide a clear discussion of the researcher's personal and professional interest in the topic of integrating SEND learners into mainstream settings and will scope the significance of investigating this topic further. The literature review will dissect existing primary and secondary data on the topic, scoping anticipated themes from SEND learners of which have been highlighted in the researcher's previous experiences in similar specialist settings. The aims of the research will be shared where the researcher will align with a qualitative interpretive paradigm which delineates the researcher's views on reality - *ontology*, the comprehension of knowledge - *epistemology*, and the values that direct their investigation - *axiology*. This will be followed by the ethical considerations that were imperative to adhere to in this research project, particularly working with vulnerable learners who share their perspectives on a sensitive matter. The methodology section will explain and justify the choice of methods that were used as part of this research project and will identify the epistemological basis of the study and link it to the research methods that were used. The findings and discussions section will present summaries and extracts from the researcher's data and show to a degree how this correlates with the research questions. This section will identify relevant themes and will link to those identified in the literature review. This section will show how the researcher questioned and discussed their own developing understanding, highlight any new themes, provide reference to existing primary and secondary data, and will be enhanced through the researcher's reflection. The final part of this paper will be an evaluation of the research where the researcher will discuss whether the aims were met. The main findings of the research will be summarised in this section and will also refer to any changes or improvements that would be made to the project if it were conducted again. The researcher will make recommendations for further research and what this should focus on before summarising what has been learnt about their conduct of educational research, scoping strengths and areas for development.

2. Rationale

My career journey in the industry of education started over five years ago. I worked as a teaching assistant through a supply agency and was asked to cover a teaching assistant's role at a secondary SEND school in Northern England. At this time, I was studying towards a BA (Bachelor of Arts) degree in Education Studies (Primary) part-time, with the intention of progressing to training to become a primary school teacher. However, after spending a few weeks working with SEND learners, I quickly found their resilience and determination inspired me as a practitioner in education, this altered my focus at the time to work towards a career in SEND education, something my passion for has, and continues, to grow every day.

Towards the end of my BA degree, I was working towards my final assignment, and I learned through my tutor that a sustainable development goal (SDG4) was agreed by the *United Nations* (2022) to 'ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all by 2030'. The notion of 'inclusion' in their goal is open to interpretation. It could imply that they recognise the importance of addressing diverse learning needs, including those learners with disabilities. This could then imply that specialised provisions are necessary in ensuring SEND learners receive appropriate support and accommodations which could include; building and upgrading education facilities that are disability-sensitive, providing safe, non-violent, inclusive, and effective learning environments for all, and/or ensuring equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for people with disabilities (*Cordonier Segger & Harrington, 2019; Unicef, 2023*). However, an argument could be made on whether this could be interpreted as integrating SEND learners into mainstream educational settings. The goal aims to overcome barriers limiting the presence, participation and achievement of learners, and focuses on strengthening the capacity of the education system to reach out to all learners. The concept of inclusive education is described as a process to ensure 'full participation and access to quality learning opportunities' for everyone (*A4ID, 2022*). As an undergraduate and a teaching assistant working in SEND education, I intended to find out what the perspectives of SEND learners, and teachers on the potential integration of SEND learners into mainstream settings, which has ultimately led to me designing and conducting this project.

After finding out about SDG4 (2022), I proceeded to compare UK SEND education with SEND education in Norway, a country 'committed to egalitarianism' (*Befring, 1990*), a philosophical and

political ideology that emphasises the equality of all individuals in terms of rights, opportunities, and social status, recognising that all people are fundamentally equal in moral and legal standing, and not be discriminated against based on their characteristics (*Arneson, 2013; Kenton, 2020*).

As a SEND practitioner, I started questioning the potential impact of integrating SEND learners into mainstream education within the UK, this is something that has been at the forefront of my mind for a long time, and something that is now at the heart of my research. I find myself conducting the research with three mindsets, or three identities, which includes; as a researcher, as a SEND practitioner, and as an advocate for SEND learners, which have influenced my axiology, my determination to conduct this research, and how my values contribute towards my long-term passion, which is the belief that those diagnosed with SEND have a right to voice their perspectives on their education. I believe the following questions need to be addressed:

- Referring to the notion of ‘inclusion’ in SDG4 (2022), based on which criteria would a SEND learner be ‘destined’ to complete their education in a specialist provision, or in a mainstream provision? How is this decided, who decides it, and why?
- Have those who have agreed to SDG4 (2022) on behalf of the UK sought the perspectives of SEND learners on this matter?
- Have those who agreed to SDG4 (2022) on behalf of the UK worked in a specialist provision for SEND learners before?

Education is paramount in every individual’s development; children, adolescents, young people and adults, and whether this is mainstream or specialist provision, does not impact education’s importance. If we interpret inclusion as integration, to what, or whose benefit is the integration of SEND learners into mainstream settings? Yes, this may benefit decisionmakers in global education, but what about the people at the heart of SEND education, the learners. In hindsight, if SDG4 was achieved in the UK tomorrow, would the learners be leaping towards their new school gates, or would they be staring out their window at home, anticipating the arrival of their escort to accompany them into the unknown? The voices of SEND learners must be heard, not ignored or unfound, after all, nothing should be done about ‘them’, without ‘them.’

I am a firm believer in ‘nothing about us, without us’ (*Charlton, 1998*). Although I have no Special Educational Needs (SEN) or have a diagnosis of SEN, I do have a disability as I have a diagnosis

of Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS). I would be enraged if those in authority decided to remove public toilet facilities without speaking to myself or others who have IBS, Chron's Disease, Colitis or any other bowel condition. Therefore, I firmly believe that the concept of integrating SEND learners into mainstream provision, whether this is the action associated with inclusion, is significant in the SEND community. Now is the time to conduct the necessary research, not on SEND learners, but with them, and with SEND teachers to gain their perspectives on this matter as time is ticking away on the 2030 countdown.

Exploring literature on the subject of my research, *Warnes. Et Al.*, (2021) identified important issues regarding inclusive education for children with SEND in England by conducting a study with teachers as participants. *Warnes. Et Al.*, (2021, p. 36) emphasised the crucial issue, as stated by a mainstream teacher, that "there are inadequate specialist staff available to support children with SEND." I will consider this in my research and would like to learn more about it from the viewpoint of a teacher who specialises in SEND. The absence of teaching aids and SEND instructional materials, as well as the idea that schools would struggle to accommodate SEND students because of their inadequate infrastructure, were two other major issues raised by *Warnes. Et Al.*, (2021) study. As a professional with experience in both mainstream and SEND settings, I find it hard to imagine SEND students feeling at ease in mainstream settings where their needs might not be satisfied. Considering the dearth of tools and resources for SEND learners in mainstream settings, as well as the infrastructure of mainstream provisions that were not designed to accommodate the needs of SEND individuals, I have used the research findings of *Warnes. Et Al.*, (2021) to further explore my imagination.

For instance, a mainstream school might not have any sensory rooms or hydrotherapy pools, but it might have a pastoral department or isolation area for students who don't follow their rules. This raises concerns about the cost and where authorities will find the psychological balance. Research suggests that the cost of integrating SEND learners into mainstream settings, taking into consideration early intervention, flexible funding, and systematic collaboration, could risk annual deficits exceeding £3 billion over three academic years, however evidence from inclusive models suggests potential savings through resource sharing and reduced bureaucratic overhead (*Halvorsen. Et Al.*, 1996; *UK Parliament*, 2025).

From a psychological standpoint, inclusion and equality are linked in the context of SEND integration into mainstream education. In light of this, how would the authorities anticipate that school leadership teams would react if a parent questioned the justice of a decision regarding her child—a "mainstream" learner—who had been placed in detention for punching a wall, as opposed to a SEND learner who had climbed the school gates to get out of the provision with no consequence? This is fictional, though very possible in a world after achieving SDG4 (2022).

According to this review of the literature, *Warnes. Et Al.*, (2021) concentrated on the viewpoints of mainstream educators in their earlier studies. Importantly, I will only be gathering the opinions of SEND teachers and students for my research project. As mentioned, their voice is crucial in determining how they will fare academically, and for those who enter the SEND community in the future after a diagnosis.

Interpreting qualitative data is my philosophical stance as an interpretivist. It is essential that I disassociate myself from identifying as a member of the SEND community because I am an outsider. But as a dedicated professional in SEND education, I think it's critical that SEND students understand the significance of their role in this issue and are heard. I consider myself fortunate to be in this role as a researcher and practitioner who fervently believes in giving the SEND community the best opportunities to live as independently as possible and to play important roles in their local communities and future workplaces.

SEND learners and practitioners can therefore seize the chance to express their viewpoints through qualitative research, and they can do so by using my interpretivist approach to make me their advocate.

3. Literature Review

Conducting a thorough literature review for this research was critical in gaining insight into existing research on the topic of integrating SEND learners into mainstream educational settings. Although the research in this area ‘had been carried out over a significant number of years and in many countries...before the implementation of the Education Act 1981’ (*Lee and Henkhuzens, 1996*), specifically focusing the research within FE, and involving the perspectives of learners is minute to non-existent. It is worth noting that the sources of information where I have acquired previous findings were published in a timeframe of around thirty years, from 1996 until now. I believe it is important to highlight this so that unbiased comparisons can be made fairly, and when scoping policies and governmental decisions, it is important to note that the UK government has switched between Conservative and Labour leadership several times in this duration.

Authoritative perspective

The first trend I noted focused on an authoritative perspective which included perspectives from the Government and Local Authorities (LA). *Lee and Henkhuzens (1996)* cited the ‘*Association of Metropolitan Authorities (1995)*’ report, who suggested that reviewing Special Educational Needs (SEN) may result in competing demands presenting challenges for authorities as they must address various types of preferences that may be hard for them to satisfy. More recently, a change in political leadership in the UK from the Conservative to the Labour Party has brought interest to the topic of SEND education. According to *Roberts (2024)*, Margaret Mulholland (SEND and inclusion specialist at the Association of School and College Leaders) noted there being a concern that integrating SEND learners into a mainstream educational setting could be viewed as a ‘cure-all’ for the intricate needs present in our educational institutions. Mulholland emphasised that schools require assistance in managing issues related to funding, space and curriculum when establishing separate provisions, and that much more effort is necessary to tackle the SEND crisis. Mulholland recommended that mainstream schools utilise additional provisions to enhance support (*Roberts, 2024*). *Roberts (2024)* stated that the Labour government has highlighted the importance of inclusivity in mainstream education. In Labour’s September 2024 conference,

Bridget Phillipson (Education Secretary) stated that the future of the educational system must embrace inclusive practices in mainstream settings, and that schools will need to accommodate a broader spectrum of often more intricate needs than they may have dealt with previously. In addition, Phillipson claimed that ‘Ministers want the vast majority of young people with SEND to be educated in mainstream schools,’ (Roberts, 2024).

SEND learners and mainstream provisions

Strogilos & Ward (2023) claimed that including SEND students in mainstream schools is prioritised in the English education system based on ‘the progressive removal of barriers to learning and participation in mainstream education’. The concept of creating inclusive educational provisions that provides for all learners regardless of the impact of their SEN condition or disability would be exceptional, however, the stark reality is that the task of doing so appears unrealistic. *Morley Et Al.*, (2020) quoted *Maher and Fitzgerald’s* (2020) work in their research which claimed that teachers questioned the appropriateness of mainstream schools for pupils with more complex learning needs, they noted that academics such as Baroness Mary Warnock, who published the Warnock Report (1978) (*Gillard*, 2012) voiced their opinions in debates about whether some pupils would be better served in special school settings. The perspectives of teachers on the idea of including SEND learners in mainstream education is an area which has been explored through previous research, and it is important that their opinions are heard as they are on the metaphorical ‘frontline’ of educating learners every day. *Morley Et Al.*, (2020) noted that teachers have shared concerns that the inclusion of SEND learners in mainstream settings may have a negative impact on other pupils, highlighting *Reyes Et Al.*, (2012) who suggested that learning and progress can be constrained if negative behaviours disrupt the learning climate, but also, on the contrary, *Oliver* (2013) who claimed that this way of thinking aligns with deficit ideologies of disability, in that it casts the pupil and their SEND as the problem. As a teacher with experience in SEND and mainstream educational settings, I know from first-hand experience that learning and progress can be negatively impacted through negative behaviours of learners, but I think it is unfair to directly associate negative behaviours with SEND learners. Any learner, SEND or mainstream, can display negative behaviours, and SEND learners are not placed in specialist provisions because of their

behaviour, it is because their needs are better met in these provisions as opposed to a mainstream provision.

Concerns

Research suggests that it is not necessarily just the behaviour of SEND learners that poses a concern for mainstream teachers on the inclusion of SEND learners in mainstream provisions. Some key themes I noted in this literature review included high levels of concern and stress, mixed attitudes towards inclusion, perceived lack of support and resources and the impact on teacher wellbeing. *Warnes Et Al.*, (2021) argued that the concern and stress element links to teachers reporting that the increasing diversity of classroom populations, especially with more SEND learners, leads to higher stress levels and feelings of being overwhelmed, as well as the expectation to constantly adapt teaching methods for individual needs in every lesson is a major source of stress as the teacher's expressed anxiety around not meeting all students' needs. *Warnes Et Al.*, (2021) did scope concerns around the possibility of behavioural issues with some SEND learners, noting that the teachers feel as they are acting as counsellors rather than educators at times. Interestingly, *Drabble* (2024) claimed that the 'Children and Families Act (2014) brought a clear expectation that most pupils with SEND would be taught in a mainstream school, and that every teacher is a teacher of SEND'. It could be argued that every teacher possesses the interpersonal skills to teach any learner regardless of whether they have a SEND diagnosis or not, this is something that is reiterated in various ways when you read the person specification attached to an advertised vacancy for a teaching position. Although teachers may have the interpersonal skills to meet this requirement, or expectation, it can be argued that they feel there is a lack of support and resources to do this effectively, which could contribute towards their concern, or stress around including SEND learners in mainstream settings.

The *Special Needs Jungle* (2024) claimed that 83% of educators believe that SEND learners are 'not being effectively supported in their aspirations and achievements by the current education system', and that 'the prevalence of SEND is one of the top three things teachers have grown more concerned about in the past year.' The report does not break down the 83% into whether the

response came from a teacher in a mainstream or specialist provision as it was conducted across education, however, reading further into the source, it appears that the larger figures filter from primary and secondary mainstream education. Looking at our current education system, there is support that is provided for SEND learners in mainstream settings, and progress has been made in areas such as creating sensory and wellbeing rooms for SEND learners, however this was more common across primary settings (*Special Needs Jungle*, 2024). *Tirraoro* (2023) reiterated that ‘inadequate support for SEND is seen as a major barrier to learning by 63% of teachers’, and *Jury Et Al.*, (2023) also noted that ‘teachers cite increased workload, inadequate training and the lack of resources as reasons for their concerns about inclusion’.

Current practice

To add context to this, in the UK, we have ARMS (Additionally Resourced Mainstream Schools) where funding is allocated to schools who invest this in areas of supporting SEND learners through the means of creating specialist units whereby specialist SEND teachers and teaching assistants are tasked with supporting the development of SEND learners whilst allowing them to remain part of the wider school community (*Harrow GOV*, 2025). In my current role as a tutor / assessor, I work with a range of teaching assistant apprentices where I support them in working towards their end-point assessment (EPA) at the end of their apprenticeship where they show an external assessor how they meet the relevant knowledge, skills and behaviours expected of a teaching assistant. One of the apprentice teaching assistants I teach is employed within the ARMS provision of a primary school setting as part of their apprenticeship. When I visited my apprentice for their first observation, I was led to a separate facility within the school, away from the classrooms which housed around 30 students each, away from the main hall and dining hall, and into an area that you can access through tapping your fob on the door sensor. The ARMS classroom was very inclusive and accommodated for around 6-8 pupils, they had their own yard, there was one SEND teacher, two SEND teaching assistants, and the apprentice teaching assistant who I taught. Another apprentice I teach who works in a mainstream secondary school works in the alternative provision (AP) area, this has been designed to support learners with SEND, or those who have Social, Emotional and Mental Health (SEMH) needs who struggle to cope with the demands of mainstream classrooms. AP settings, serving 48,000 pupils annually, face unique belonging

challenges. The 2023 Plan reimagines AP as a "therapeutic service" with reintegration goals, however, Ofsted reports that only 33% of AP pupils return to mainstream education, highlighting the need for stronger belonging bridges (GOV UK, 2023). I visited my apprentice during their induction and saw the alternative provision area and was led to a separate building on the school's site where these SEND / SEMH learners were housed for their education. My experience of ARMS provisions and alternative provisions within mainstream settings is that they appear more of a segregation as opposed to integration for SEND / SEMH learners. The struggle of comprehension lies within the funding and resources being available but appears to be spent on creating a sense of segregation as opposed to the inclusion, or integration of SEND learners into mainstream settings, thus creating an imbalance between the perspectives of teachers and their interpretation of how inclusion looks which could be based on their experiences if they have worked in similar settings as I described above. The attitudes of teachers towards inclusion are mixed, *Monsen., Et Al.*, (2014) claimed that there are teachers who are willing to implement inclusion if adequate support is provided, whilst others feel that inclusion can be detrimental to non-SEND pupils or feel that some SEND learners require more support than what mainstream provisions can offer.

It appears that there is no conclusive perspective of mainstream teachers on the inclusion of SEND learners into mainstream settings, if you conducted research with one hundred mainstream teachers with the aim of identifying a perspective that was conclusive in this matter, you would have one hundred different opinions, because teaching is unique. As a practitioner in education, in my experience of supporting and delivering learning, every teacher has their own unique way of teaching that cannot be replicated, therefore I can only assume that the concerns of mainstream educators on the inclusion of SEND learners is influenced through their interpretation of how this would impact their planning, preparation and delivery, as well as their ability to manage their classroom effectively.

The perspectives of SEND learners and their integration into mainstream education.

The aims of my research focuses on exploring the perspectives of teachers and SEND learners on the idea of integrating SEND learners into mainstream educational settings, in the next part of my literature review, I will be focusing more on existing literature around the perspectives of SEND learners in mainstream settings, however, I feel that it is important to note that research with SEND

learners on this matter has not been conducted previously, there is a lot of material that focuses on the learners from the perspectives of others, for example, teachers, parents and stakeholders. As a professional who has worked in education for a long time, SEND education is my specialism and I have a wealth of experience in this field, the aim of my research is something I have been interested in for several years. I have had the opportunity to gain an existing understanding of the perspectives of previous SEND learners on the idea of being integrated into mainstream settings out of curiosity before I planned this research. The common themes I noted throughout my conversations when working with SEND learners that I will be exploring in more depth are anxiety, familiarity and sense of belonging.

Anxiety

Laven (2022) argued that all students will feel an element of anxiety when at school, but there are several factors which cause additional anxiety for students with SEND including their feeling of being left behind in terms of their learning and progress, as opposed to their mainstream peers, creating a sense of frustration and anxiety. *Laven* (2022) also argued that SEND students may struggle with socialisation, resulting in isolation and potentially seeking attention through misbehaviour. Falling behind in education and feeling isolated could consequently lead to the student being bullied, which again will contribute to their anxiety. *Chante-Marie* (2023) noted that isolation is problematic for SEND students in mainstream settings, this can be done indirectly through the forms of providing alternative materials, assigning a teaching assistant to a SEND learner, or temporarily separating SEND learners from the rest of the classroom. This also links to situations where the ‘negative emotional and behavioural consequences of young people not having their needs understood or met’ were described as ‘messaging around’ and ‘distracting others’ – further associating, or labelling SEND learners as ‘naughty’ (*Chante-Marie*, 2023). *Kids.org* (2023) noted that there are common triggers in anxiety for ‘young people with SEND which includes routine changes, sensory overload and school pressure...feeling overwhelmed in new environments or struggling to understand social cues.’ As a professional who has worked in both mainstream and specialist educational provisions, there are many differences that should be highlighted between both provisions which adds to the claims of these authors. For instance, I have experienced both mainstream and specialist provisions for Secondary Education (SE) and Further

Education (FE). In hindsight, if I visualised the settings and took away the learners, the infrastructure of the settings is designed appropriately for the population of who attends the setting. For example, most mainstream SE and FE settings are built to accommodate over a thousand pupils, they may include several buildings, they may have one or more dining halls that accommodate hundreds of pupils at one time, corridors are furnished with lockers and lead to many different classrooms, all of which contain displays of work that have been produced by higher-ability learners. In contrast, the infrastructure of a SEND provision, SE or FE, are designed smaller, it's likely that there will only be one building, one main dining / sports hall, widened corridors which are furnished with coat pegs and provide a pathway to several classrooms, but also sensory rooms, and rooms that are designed to support learners in developing life skills, and displays are designed to celebrate the achievements of learners, or show what they have been participating in, whereas mainstream provisions may display a timeline of historical events in Britain, which is important for those in mainstream education, but would be less important for the majority of learners in a specialist provision. Factors such as the infrastructure and interior design of provisions may not be considered a priority in the matter of integrating SEND learners into mainstream settings, however these factors contribute to the educational experience, and a SEND learner could find this overwhelming considering sensory overload, and being immersed in structured settings, ultimately impacting their anxiety (*Brown, 2024; Leese, 2025*).

Familiarity

Schinariol (2024) stated that 'the heart of a SEND school is its ability to create an inclusive and accommodating learning environment for students...the schools are built around the idea that every child deserves an education tailored to their skills and needs.' There are several reasons why a learner is educated at a specialist provision, as opposed to a mainstream provision including tailored educational approaches, resource and expertise gaps in mainstream schools, environmental adaptations, legal and systematic factors, and outcomes and transition planning. A SEND learner is likely to either have only experienced specialist educational provision, primary through to FE, or has transitioned from a mainstream provision to a specialist provision because their needs could not be met in the mainstream setting. Although integrating students with SEND into mainstream classrooms is the goal of inclusive education, it might not be the best strategy for

all individuals. Specialised and individualised help that may not be easily accessible in a typical classroom setting is provided by SEND schools, which supplement the mainstream educational system (*Schinariol, 2024*). Familiarity is a key factor that would need to be considered in the integration of SEND learners into mainstream provisions.

Familiarity is a broad term when we associate it with SEND learners as it could include a range of factors such as teaching and support, friendships and relationships, and preparation for adulthood. It could also include accessibility which links to the design and space of the provision, knowing how to get to and from the provision, and being able to access facilities such as sensory rooms or hydrotherapy pools which could be limited or non-existent in mainstream settings. Within specialist provisions, visual timetables and clear daily routines are often implemented to help SEND learners anticipate transitions and activities which helps reduce uncertainty (*Hawkins & Nest, 2023; Haringey London, 2024*). SEND learners typically interact with the same trained staff, fostering trust and reducing stress associated with unfamiliar faces (*Haringey London, 2024*). Although visual timetables and clear daily routines could be designed to support SEND learners in mainstream settings, this could lead to isolation and anxiety as noted previously due to SEND learners being treated differently to their peers. Specialist provisions are sensory-friendly designed, for example, lighting, acoustics, and spatial layouts are adapted to minimise sensory overload, as well as include sensory rooms or low-arousal areas to help learners self-regulate during overwhelming moments (*Hawkins & Nest, 2023; Haringey London, 2024*). In addition, in specialist provisions, there is an emphasis on independence and confidence where teaching assistants and staff are trained to promote self-reliance rather than dependency, using tools like visual aids and structured prompts, and learners' abilities are highlighted to build resilience and engagement (*Leicester City Council, 2021; Haringey London, 2024*). Through relational consistency, instructional approaches that meet the cognitive, sensory, and emotional demands of SEND learners, and environmental design, familiarity with specialist offerings is methodically constructed (*Hawkins & Nest, 2023; Haringey London, 2024*), specialist initiatives have been tailored to fill these gaps via fundamental modifications and staff training, whereas mainstream schools do not possess the tools or expertise to regularly offer a comparable level of familiarity (*Leicester City Council, 2021; Ofsted, 2021*). Deeper academic and interpersonal affiliation requires familiarity as a prerequisite. For overcoming the negative feelings, such as dread or anxiety, that frequently accompany a significant life transition, this early stage of belonging is essential

(Kahu. Et Al. 2022). According to research, familiarity is one of the themes that promote SEND students' sense of belonging at school, along with inclusion, support, and identification (Lovell. Et Al., 2022).

Sense of belonging

The broad definition of belonging in the context of SEND education is a student's perception of their own importance in the class or school's life and of being accepted, valued, included, and encouraged by others in the school community (Long and Guo, 2023; NEU, 2023). For SEND learners in a specialist provision, acceptance, value and inclusion is enhanced through similarity in terms of overcoming barriers to learning together, role-modelling resilience and being encouraged to fulfil potential by peers and educators. This is also reflected in mainstream educational settings; however, learner progression contributes towards league tables that rank provisions based on summative success. Whereas progression for a SEND learner in a specialist provision is individualised, highlighted through their progress towards meeting personal targets and achieving Educational Health Care Plan (EHCP) outcomes (RTRIIBE, 2023; Schinariol, 2024).

Where a SEND learner has a sense of belonging, this leads to a cycle of benefits towards personal development which includes the impact on their mental health and wellbeing, academic benefits and educational progress, and the reduction of alienation and exclusion. Focusing on their mental health and wellbeing, the psychological benefits encompass both good features of psychological functioning and the absence of adverse mental health outcomes. SEND learners who feel like they belong grow more confident in their identities and skills, which promotes a more positive self-concept. Increased self-perception triggers a beneficial chain reaction in which greater mental health leads to improved learning and social engagement, which in turn strengthens belonging and improves mental health outcomes (UCL, 2020). However, the historical background of systematic exclusion must be taken into consideration while analysing the educational experience of students with SEND. Until legislation such as the *Education Act* (1981), there was no expectation that children with disabilities should or could attend public schools, this was a right, but not a legal one until the implementation of the *Education Act* (1996) which allowed disabled young people and their parents to legally access a mainstream placement if successful on appeal. As educational

systems continue to move away from highly ingrained segregation practices, this historical viewpoint helps explain why belonging continues to be a difficulty for SEND learners.

A sense of belonging protects against exclusion and alienation. Students who do not feel like they belong are more likely to miss school, become disengaged, and eventually be expelled, according to research (Lovell. *Et Al.*, 2022; NEU, 2023; Sims, 2024, *South Gloucestershire Educational Psychology Service*; 2024). Fostering belonging is particularly important for SEND students, who are already more likely to be excluded. Students are less inclined to look for belonging in less prosocial groups or situations when schools foster a friendly and inclusive environment, and exclusion rates dramatically decline (NEU, 2023; *South Gloucestershire Educational Psychology Service*, 2024). Belonging not only enhances academic and wellbeing outcomes but also increases resilience, reducing young people's susceptibility to exclusionary influences, according to government guidelines and toolkits. Prosocial behaviour, improved mental health, and a stronger feeling of agency are all associated with a sense of belonging, and these factors all lessen the probability of disruptive activity or withdrawal that might result in exclusion. On the other hand, alienation and exclusion can have detrimental effects, such as increased social isolation or participation in illicit activities, (NEU, 2023; *South Gloucestershire Educational Psychology Service*, 2024).

Ultimately, for SEND learners, belonging is essential to improved mental health and wellbeing, academic success and protection from exclusion, not only a social or emotional requirement. Educational achievements and the general well-being of SEND pupils are shown to improve in schools that promote belonging through inclusive policies and practices (Lovell. *Et Al.*, 2022; NEU, 2023; Sims, 2024; *South Gloucestershire Educational Psychology Service*, 2024).

4. Research Aims & Ethical Issues

The aim of this research was to explore the perspectives of SEND learners and teachers on the idea of integrating SEND learners into mainstream educational settings. This research encompasses a qualitative interpretive paradigm to envisage and illustrate their perspectives (*Pervin and Mokhtar, 2022; Nickerson, 2024*). Their responses were systematically analysed, interpreted, and presented to illuminate their perspectives. Establishing a research paradigm prior to performing research is crucial as it furnishes the conceptual basis that influences all facets of the research process. A research paradigm delineates the researcher's views on reality - *ontology*, the comprehension of knowledge - *epistemology*, and the values that direct their investigation - *axiology*, (*Guraya. Et Al., 2023; Pretorius, 2024*).

Interpretivism focusses on how individuals derive meaning from their daily occurrences, surroundings, and identities, a process shaped by personal histories, cultural settings, and social interactions (*Hammersley & Traianou, 2012; Pervin and Mokhtar, 2022*). This methodology emphasises subjective lived experiences, examining how individuals navigate and understand their social environments (*Yin, 2016*). This research aims to accurately capture the varied experiences and understandings of participants by aligning with this paradigm (*Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018*). Positivism typically adheres to quantitative methodology for data gathering and analysis (*Pretorius, 2024*), aiming for repeatable findings. This study seeks to comprehend an individual's experience or perception of reality (*Poucher. Et Al., 2019; Junjie and Yingxin, 2022*), indicating an alignment with an interpretivist approach that is more advantageous for supporting the study's outcomes.

To effectively utilise this interpretivist qualitative paradigm, the use of open questioning and participant visualisation methods were employed to formulate an illustration of their perspective. Visual methods are particularly effective for engaging participants from diverse linguistic, cultural, or cognitive backgrounds, allowing them to convey experiences that may be challenging to express verbally (*Ong, 2020*). To gain insight on the perspectives of SEND learners on being integrated into mainstream educational settings, five participants were selected, each with a SEND diagnosis and enrolled onto a Further Education programme through the Local Authority (LA) and attended a specialist education provision for young people between the ages of 18-24 years old. Embracing

an interpretivist paradigm proved beneficial for understanding learners' experiences and their perceptions of these realities. This investigation adopts a relativist ontology, emphasising the existence of multiple realities that are socially constructed and influenced by individual perspectives and cultural contexts (*Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Poucher. Et Al., 2019*). Reality is perceived as fluid and contingent upon social constructs (*Levers, 2013*). This investigation aimed to give SEND learners a voice in their education, providing an opportunity for them to express their opinions on potential integration into mainstream educational settings.

To align with the interpretivist qualitative paradigm, various methods for information gathering were evaluated. Focus groups serve as a valuable technique for data collection in qualitative research; however, concerns regarding potential impacts on the validity of results must be acknowledged. Focus groups are susceptible to bias and influence from group members, potentially affecting the validity of the results (*Leung and Savithiri, 2009*). Additionally, sensitive topics may pose challenges in focus group discussions (*Luke and Goodrich, 2019*). The intention of this research was to explore learners' perspectives, which could be a delicate matter, underscoring the inappropriateness of this approach (*Leung and Savithiri, 2009*).

Structured interviews were also considered as a method to gather participants' experiences; however, upon examining the specific characteristics of structured interviews, I concluded that this approach would not be advantageous. Structured interviews exhibit limitations in flexibility due to their reliance on closed questioning. Consequently, if rephrasing of questions is necessary for the participant's comprehension, which is likely when researching with SEND learners, such adjustments cannot be made (*Orvaschel, 2006*). Moreover, a formal approach, such as those used in structured interviews, can hinder rapport-building with interviewees, potentially affecting the openness and honesty of responses in their language (*Knott. Et Al., 2022*). Thus, it is demonstrated that semi-structured interviews are more effective in addressing the research questions (*Orvaschel, 2006; Knott. Et Al., 2022*).

Researchers must address several ethical considerations in any research or investigation (*BERA, 2024*). Prior to the study, the questions for SEND learners were evaluated by my supervisor and the ethics council of my post-graduate institution, as well as my colleagues (tutors and management) who work with the participants daily, along with obtaining agreement from the

gatekeeper. Before commencing the study, participants were informed that they might withdraw at any moment without affecting their academic advancement (BERA, 2024). Participants granted written consent following a comprehensive briefing on the study. The technique was documented for participants, specifying their role in the interviews, the methods of data collection, storage, and utilisation, as well as the procedures for opting out if preferred. Participants were explicitly informed that they might terminate the interview or retract their consent at any moment during the procedure. To uphold ethical standards, I emphasised that participation would be completely voluntary and devoid of coercion. Moreover, individuals would provide both their consent and assent (BERA, 2024).

Alongside the previously mentioned measures, additional departure procedures were instituted to guarantee participant wellbeing. This involved notifying educational practitioners in the setting of the study process—specifically, the activities occurring, their timing, and the potential support needed. Consultation and direction were obtained from the provision’s practitioners encompassing any suggestions they offered. To alleviate any anxiety, participants received the interview questions beforehand. This provided them with an opportunity to contemplate the themes and evaluate the potential effects on their wellness, while also permitting me to maintain objectivity and facilitate their self-expression. This also allowed me as the researcher to gain approval from the participant that they fully understood the questions as they had been designed to reflect their level of comprehension with support from practitioners working in the setting. Participants were guaranteed, both in writing and verbally, that all perspectives and opinions expressed during the interviews would be kept confidential, in accordance with the *Data Protection Act* (2018) legislation. A de-identification process was implemented, providing pseudonyms to each participant to safeguard their identities (Olmos-Vega. *Et al.*, 2022, BERA, 2024) and mitigate concerns over the dissemination or exposure of their opinions that could jeopardise their reputations (Hammersley and Traianou, 2012).

To mitigate interviewer bias, a deliberate effort was undertaken to promote participants' candid expression of their thoughts, perspectives, and experiences. This methodology sought to decrease the likelihood of the researcher forming assumptions (Hammersley and Traianou, 2012). To augment deidentification, individual interviews were employed rather than focus groups. This

decision also considered issues regarding peer influence, which could possibly compromise participants' honesty and transparency (Cohen. *Et Al.*, 2017).

Data was captured with a local authorities' voice recording tool on my work iPad and securely archived on my student account, adhering to corporate data protection rules. Each tape was later transcribed and anonymised to ensure confidentiality. All students involved in the study had a SEND diagnosis with an EHCP in place and satisfied supplementary criteria to correspond with my research objectives and epistemological framework.

Confidentiality was also integral to the design, dissemination and data collection for the teachers' questionnaire. By using Google Forms I was able to maintain confidentiality in my research due to its robust security and privacy features which includes encryption, access control, authentication, and compliance with the *Data Protection Act* (2018). Google Forms guarantees that data provided by participants is encrypted during transmission and while stored. This safeguards responses from interception or unauthorised access during transmission and while stored on Google's servers (Bobirca, 2024; Jotform, 2023). As a researcher, I could control who can access the form and the collected data. At the organisation where I conducted this research, all members of staff have a Google account created for working purposes, therefore when completing the form, they were required to sign into their account, and I could limit access to these individuals only. Google Forms is designed to help users comply with regulations like the *Data Protection Act* (2018) and allowed me to configure settings appropriately to inform participants about data use and storage (Bobirca, 2024; Jotform, 2023).

5. Methodology

The study involved eight participants, five SEND learners and three SEND teachers, with *Denzin & Lincoln* (2018) advocating for a purposeful rather than random sampling approach due to the small size. *Morantes-Africano* (2023) contended that a smaller, more targeted sample size would be advantageous as it guarantees the selection of appropriate participants aligned with the research objective. A purposive sample method was employed to examine the phenomena under consideration. This approach entailed the selection of participants who satisfied defined SEND criteria (an existing EHCP), as well as the selection of experienced SEND teachers, so guaranteeing that their experiences were pertinent and capable of yielding significant insights into the research enquiries under consideration (*Moser & Korstjens*, 2018).

This purposeful sampling was crucial in terms of identifying suitable SEND learners as participants as it required individuals who were enrolled in a FE program, possessed an EHCP plan, and were willing to candidly share their opinions and experiences to address the research issues. While not all SEND learners refrain from expressing their ideas and experiences, a considerable number exhibit a propensity to do so, driven by apprehensions regarding judgement, misinterpretation, or adverse repercussions. Therefore, establishing a supportive, empathetic, and inclusive atmosphere is essential for motivating SEND learners to express their perspectives candidly (*ONS*, 2021; *Silas*, 2023; *Taylor*, 2023). Research suggests that the use of semi-structured interviews would be suitable for collecting qualitative data from SEND learners as they provide the flexibility, depth, and conducive atmosphere necessary for SEND learners to express their perspectives and experiences more candidly than with many other study methodologies (*DeJonckheere & Vaughn*, 2019; *George*, 2022; *Amjad & Malik*, 2024). In comparison, structured interviews are contended to offer restricted depth, exhibit reduced adaptability to unique communication requirements, and may hinder SEND learners' capacity to articulate intricate experiences (*George*, 2022). The use of questionnaires with SEND learners may be efficient in large-scale research projects, however from a research perspective, they provide limited depth to explore, and fixed questioning may not capture nuanced experiences, hence their unsuitability for SEND learners who may need support to articulate their thoughts (*Hecker & Kalpokas*, 2025). Owing to limited time constraints, five students, of whom were enrolled onto FE

programmes at the researcher's provision, were consulted regarding their perspectives on participating in this study. To guarantee the appropriate students were selected, I leveraged my social capital to identify individuals willing to participate in the study (*Alpino and Mehlum, 2021*). While social capital may influence the thoroughness of research (*Alpino and Mehlum, 2021*), I remained cognisant of my reflexivity (*Olmos-Vega. Et Al., 2022*). During the research, I remained cognisant of my reflexivity and preconceived notions regarding learners' responses, my bias towards SEND education, and the potential influence of these factors on the research design (*Olmos-Vega. Et Al., 2022*). Before the commencement of the interviews, all participants were informed that I sought only candid comments, regardless of whether they were positive, negative, or impartial; their genuine opinions were of paramount importance. This underscores my understanding of relational reflexivity (*Deer, 2008*) and its potential influence on the feasibility of research (*McConnell-Henry. Et Al., 2010*). The questions employed were deliberated with my colleagues who taught the participants to guarantee they could not be perceived as coercive (*Denzin & Lincoln, 2018*). Furthermore, all interviews are included in the appendix to enhance transparency (see *Appendices 1 and 2*). All participants were assured that their opinions, ideas, and emotions were being examined solely from an academic standpoint, and that this information would not be disclosed to others, which could affect their reputation.

As a researcher, collaborating with colleagues necessitated my assumption of an "insider" role. This offers benefits, including enhanced accessibility and a more profound contextual comprehension, nevertheless, it presented issues such as profession duality and indistinct borders between professional and research affiliations. I recognised that familiarity with participants may influence the candidness of their information sharing and my interpretation of their responses (*Wilson. Et Al., 2022*). Moreover, I recognised that my colleagues' perception of my role as a peer can affect their comfort in participating, the honesty of their responses, and their readiness to share sensitive information. The beliefs and expectations regarding my co-workers may influence the data collection and analysis, frequently in an unconscious manner (*Holmes, 2020; Wilson. Et Al., 2022; Gurr. Et Al., 2024*). I recognised that my role as a colleague may influence not only data collecting but also the formulation of research questions, selection of methodology, and interpretation of findings (*Holmes, 2020; Wilson. Et Al., 2022; Gurr. Et Al., 2024*). Consequently, it was imperative to critically examine my own beliefs, prejudices, and influences. During the study design and data collecting phases, I consistently contemplated how my familiarity with

teaching participants, my position within the organisation, and my own values and views may influence the research process and outcomes. Thus, transparency with the participants was essential in this study; I emphasised that I desired their authentic viewpoints on the subject of SEND integration into mainstream educational settings, and that my interaction with them should not affect the correctness of their responses (Sybing, 2024; Wilson. Et Al., 2022; Gurr. Et Al., 2024).

Questionnaires, particularly self-administered formats, provide swift data gathering from various co-workers concurrently and can offer a degree of anonymity, potentially fostering more candid replies on sensitive issues (Bhandari, 2022). The use of structured questionnaires provide uniformity in the enquiries posed, facilitating the comparison of replies across participants (Kelley. Et Al., 2003; Cleave, 2023). In this research project, I recognised that the use of questionnaires as opposed to conducting interviews with colleagues would be more appropriate. The use of interviews with colleagues may have resulted in the participants experiencing pressure to provide responses they see as expected or acceptable in the workplace, rather than articulating their genuine ideas, particularly considering the sensitivity of the subject which in turn would hinder the veracity and profundity of the data gathered (Coar & Sim, 2009; Whorton, 2016; Satter, 2025). Moreover, acquaintance between myself and participants may induce bias. As the interviewer, I may have inadvertently steered the dialogue, evaded difficult enquiries, or interpreted answers through the prism of my own experiences, thereby compromising impartiality and the quality of data (Whorton, 2016).

Consequently, the use of Google Forms (see *Appendix 1*) allowed me as a researching colleague to adjust settings to prevent the collection of email addresses or personal identifiers, thereby safeguarding respondent anonymity—an essential factor in obtaining candid feedback from colleagues (Valtonen, 2024). In addition, considering time constraints and cost, Google Forms is complimentary and permits a limitless number of enquiries and replies, rendering it a pragmatic choice for workplace research (Melo, 2018; Valtonen, 2024). Furthermore, this proved to be beneficial in my data analysis where responses via Google Forms are gathered automatically and may be monitored in real time. Data can also be transferred to Google Sheets (see *Appendix 3*) for efficient analysis, facilitating the organisation and interpretation of results (Kaluza, 2023; Valtonen, 2024).

Problems encountered with methods used

Although the methods used were deemed appropriate as outlined above, it was difficult as a novice researcher to foresee forthcoming dilemmas that would impact the research project. For instance, I expected that all five SEND professionals would participate in the questionnaire to furnish qualitative data. This assumption frequently arises from inexperience and unfamiliarity with the intricacies of participant recruitment and engagement. It is proposed that inexperienced researchers may not predict issues such as participant resistance, non-responsiveness, or disengagement, and may underestimate the complexities of fostering active engagement (*Kalman, 2019*). To address this, I should have considered engaging non-respondents through concise surveys or interviews to ascertain their motivations for non-participation. This can assist in identifying systemic disparities between respondents and non-respondents, facilitating modifications in analysis or interpretation (*Halbesleben & Whitman, 2012*).

Furthermore, disregarding time-constraints proved problematic in my research project. It is argued that numerous novice researchers underestimate the time necessary for different phases of a research project, frequently owing to inexperience with the intricacies of planning, prioritising, and managing multiple simultaneous activities (*Kulkarni, 2021; Garg, 2025*). Organising, conducting and transcribing semi-structured interviews required more time than I initially anticipated. In future research, I will acknowledge that proficient time management is crucial for research progress, therefore acquiring the ability to assign pragmatic timelines for each phase, including potential delays and unforeseen obstacles (*Kulkarni, 2021; Garg, 2025*) will be paramount.

Ultimately, as this is my first research project, my lack of familiarity with various research methodologies, data gathering approaches, and analytical tools is a significant obstacle. As an inexperienced researcher, it is suggested that I may lack a comprehensive understanding of the philosophical foundations or practical necessities of the selected techniques, leading to methodological ambiguity or inconsistency (*Khankeh. Et Al., 2015; Zafar. Et Al., 2021*).

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA)

RTA was employed to elucidate the opinions of students and instructors regarding the purported integration into mainstream education. Braun and Clarke's (Naeem. *Et Al.*, 2023) Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) was utilised to analyse and interpret this material. This facilitated the identification of pertinent subjects within the data, which were subsequently consolidated into themes. Naeem. *Et Al.*, (2023) outlined the six phases of RTA:

1. **Transcription & Familiarisation** - This constitutes the preliminary stage of the theme analysis process. It entails the transcription of material and the acquisition of familiarity with it. Researchers thoroughly analyse the text to identify preliminary themes and significant portions. They subsequently choose quotations that vividly illustrate the facts and effectively embody various perspectives and trends relevant to the study aims. In my research, this phase triggered during the conduction and transcription of the semi-structured interviews with SEND learners where I scoped themes relevant to the concept of integration, considering what I found through in my literature review. In the teachers' questionnaire, this stage triggered when exporting data to a spreadsheet where I was able to identify shared perspectives and concerns of SEND practitioners.
2. **Selection of keywords** - This step entails meticulous analysis of the data, whether derived from interviews, focus groups, or visual materials. Researchers recognise reoccurring patterns, terminology, or visual components and classify them as keywords. These keywords encapsulate the experiences and perspectives of participants and are directly sourced from the data. In the semi-structured interviews, keywords or phrases that I selected included those that related to anxiety, nervousness, familiarity with the specialist provision, and what contributes towards feeling a sense of belonging. In the questionnaire, I selected keywords and phrases that linked with support and resources, learner development and the potential impact of integration.
3. **Coding** - In the third phase, brief phrases or terms, referred to as codes, are allocated to segments of data that encapsulate the material's fundamental meaning, importance, or subject. This stage streamlines intricate textual material by converting it into a theoretical framework and aids in pinpointing features pertinent to the research topics. In this research, the coding phase was critical. I focused on the keywords and phrases presented to me in

my data collection from both SEND learners and practitioners. This allowed me to understand how their angle will contribute towards the aims of the research, scoping the importance of the data.

- 4. Theme Development** - Theme development entails categorising codes into coherent groupings to discern patterns and correlations, ultimately providing insights into the study subject. In this phase, the researcher shifts from an exhaustive examination of codes and categories to a more abstract interpretation through the formulation of themes. In this phase, I was able to organise the codes into groups which enabled me to identify patterns which offered further insight into the research question. I was able to identify a range of themes from the semi-structured interviews and the questionnaire which both provided a more in-depth analysis to me, probing how I then interpreted the data.
- 5. Conceptualisation** - This phase, conceptualisation, entails comprehending and delineating concepts derived from the data. Researchers discern social trends and distil them into definitions that correspond with their investigations. In this phase I was able to identify social patterns from the data collected and refined them into anecdotes that aligned with my research. I was able to then analyse the quality of the data based on its accuracy, reliability and applicability – and scoped how they contributed to the theory and practice that relates to the subject of integrating SEND learners into mainstream provisions.
- 6. Development of Conceptual Model** - The concluding phase of the thematic analysis involves the formulation of a conceptual model. This method entails generating a distinctive representation of the data, frequently informed by established beliefs. The model addresses the research issues and highlights the study's contribution to knowledge. This stage is the conclusion of the study, summarising the results and insights obtained from the data. In the final stage, I was able to create a representation of the data and linked this to existing research on integration, which was limited. As stated, this research did not aim to answer the question at hand, however, I noted that the data collected, and using RTA, I recognised that it contributes knowledge about SEND inclusion or integration.

6. Findings & Discussion

In this section, thematic analysis is used to investigate SEND learners' perspectives of being integrated into mainstream educational settings, as well as to present themes which have been generated through responses of teachers working with SEND learners on the same concept. Themes have been developed with consideration based on the comprehension and interpretation of the responses from SEND learners to the questions asked to them in semi-structured interviews. The feedback from SEND teaching practitioners have contributed to the themes that have been identified through analysis of their responses to the SEND teacher questionnaire (see *Appendix 2*).

The themes identified from SEND learners include:

- 6.1 – Anxiety.
- 6.2 – Familiarity.
- 6.3 – A Sense of belonging.

The themes identified in the SEND teacher questionnaire include:

- 6.4 – An atomistic approach.
- 6.5 – The 'spiralling gap'.
- 6.6 – Lack of awareness.

6.1 –Anxiety

In the semi-structured interviews with SEND learners, 80% expressed a feeling of anxiety towards being integrated into mainstream educational settings. For instance, after asking the participants to visualise they are going to be asked to change settings where they would leave their current ‘specialist’ provision and will attend a ‘typical’ educational setting, I asked the participants to describe their feelings around the scenario I had described to them. Student ‘S1’ stated:

“Scared, how would everyone think of me, and if they would laugh at me, I would get worked up, and cry.” (S1)

This was reinforced by student ‘S5’:

“Probably makes me feel a bit anxious., I wouldn’t know what bus to get and would meet new tutors.” (S5).

Identifying the cause of anxiety among SEND learners is debatable as this would depend on their interpretation of the scenario I described to them. On the contrary, it could be argued that the anxiety has been created through experience, though the learners had not attended mainstream provision, their relationships or experiences with others outside of education could contribute towards how they envisage mainstream education. *ONS* (2021) suggested via their statistics in the 2021 Census that SEND learners may juxtapose themselves with peers or siblings in mainstream schools, thereby intensifying emotions of divergence, inadequacy, or the compulsion to conform. This social comparison may heighten anxiety, particularly if individuals view others as managing better or assimilating more effortlessly. The presence of friends or relatives in the same mainstream setting can exacerbate apprehensions over being picked out for assistance or seeming distinct. Certain SEND learners exhibit a pronounced aversion to being perceived as different, and the awareness that those in their proximity may observe their challenges or adjustments might exacerbate these concerns (*ONS*, 2021).

Participant (S4) response to the question posed above stated:

“Feel good – feel alright.” (S4).

An argument could be made towards S4's comprehension around the question based on their ability being lower than that of fellow participants, this is recognised through S4 working towards a lower English qualification and the struggle to verbalise their thoughts. However, according to *ONS* (2021) there is sometimes a perception that mainstream schools offer a broader academic curriculum, which can be appealing to some learners, particularly in relation to post-secondary opportunities. Moreover, certain learners will appreciate the chance to interact with or participate in lessons with mainstream peers, while a portion seeks increased access to mainstream classes or a broader array of academic disciplines, which they consider vital for their interests or future ambitions (*ONS*, 2021; *E&T Inspectorate*, 2024).

The responses from participants 'S2' and 'S3' imply that they felt more nervous towards the concept of integrating into mainstream education:

"A bit nervous and stuff, a bit wary about the place and stuff, meeting new people is a worry, obviously I will get to know them, but it is a new setting that is not familiar to me."
(S2)

"Probably feel a bit nervous meeting new people." (S3)

Describing their feeling as more 'nervous' as opposed to 'anxious' suggests that there is an element of apprehension in their feeling, though it appears to be less intense of that suggested by participants 'S1' and 'S5'. Nervousness is typically less intense and may even stimulate preparation or improve performance. Anxiety can become more severe, overwhelming, and may disrupt everyday functioning and overall well-being (*Santos-Longhurst*, 2019; *Elmer*, 2022). The responses from participants 'S2' and 'S3' suggest that their feeling towards changing to a 'typical' setting is less intense than an anxious feeling, though an argument could be made which queries their articulation of 'nervousness' which often interlinks with anxiety. The participants may see these as equal in terms of impact, or their vocabulary could be limited. To gain a more accurate interpretation of their feeling, this is an area I should have investigated further when collecting data so that I could determine whether the participants understood the differences between nervousness and anxiety.

6.2 – Familiarity

Familiarity is defined as ‘a good knowledge of something, or the fact that you know it so well’ (*Cambridge Dictionary, 2025*). The SEND learners I interviewed had only experienced specialist provision for their education since leaving primary education (ages 4-11 years old). In my interviews with the participants, after asking them to imagine that they were attending a mainstream educational provision, I questioned them on whether they would miss anything from what they are used to in their specialist setting:

“Yes, I would miss the teachers and how they help me with my learning.” (S1)

“No, I might miss certain tutors.” (S2)

“Miss the staff – because I am used to them, and I have been here a while.” (S5)

Teacher attachment is commonly affiliated with students at primary level. Studies grounded on attachment theory indicate that primary school educators frequently function as attachment figures and emotionally stable bases for young children, who seek solace, reassurance, and closeness to their teachers in manners like to their relationships with parents (*Spilt and Koomen, 2022*). It could be argued that this attachment is shared by SEND learners who attend specialist provisions as their emotional and social development often mirrors the level of learners within primary settings. Specialist provisions aim to deliver exceptional, individualised assistance tailored to the distinct requirements of each learner. The relationships between staff and learners are fundamental to this method. Guidance and best practices for SEND settings continually underscore the significance of establishing robust, trustworthy relationships with learners, since these relationships are essential for emotional stability, engagement, and academic advancement. Educators and support personnel in specialised provisions frequently receive training in attachment and trauma-informed methodologies, acknowledging that SEND learners may exhibit heightened sensitivity to alterations in routine or the absence of familiar carers (*Haringey London, 2024; Thompson & Walsh, 2024*).

Moreover, a SEND learner may become attached to their peers in a specialist setting:

“I will miss seeing my old friends from here.” (S3)

Referring to the experiences of non-SEND learners, missing peers is common in educational transitions, whether this refers to transitions from primary to secondary schools, or from secondary to further education. It is common for friendships to fade when individuals progress to different settings which causes distress and uncertainty, however, non-SEND learners will find they have the capability to adapt in their new setting where they can form relationships with their new peers. On the other hand, learners with SEND may have supplementary obstacles in establishing new friendships throughout educational changes which includes relocating to a different environment. These issues may encompass obstacles in social communication, apprehension regarding unfamiliar locations, and interruptions to established routines and support systems. Concerns regarding the formation and sustenance of friendships are prevalent, and social integration is a critical component of transition planning for SEND learners (*Davies, 2015; Inness, 2024*).

Familiarity, in the sense of relationships with teachers and peers, was a theme I anticipated before conducting my research. Having worked in SEND education for several years, I was able to draw from my understanding of the holistic support that is provided to learners in these settings. For instance, class sizes are very small compared to what is typically seen in mainstream settings. This allows learners to build more trusting relationships with teachers and their peers. The teachers and teaching assistants can provide tailored support to learners because they have the capacity to do so, whereas in a mainstream classroom, it is likely that there would only be one teacher who delivers to around thirty students. In addition, referring to my own experience, it is less common for mainstream secondary and further education settings to have teaching assistants in classrooms. With class sizes being smaller in specialist provisions, you will typically find that there are around 2-3 friendship groups in a class, whereas in a mainstream classroom, it is likely that there will be more friendship groups. Therefore, the sense of unfamiliarity for SEND learners being integrated into mainstream settings is enforced through them envisaging pre-existing friendship groups, and teachers not providing the tailored support required to best support their learning.

6.3 – Sense of belonging.

A sense of belonging is the personal perception of being welcomed, included, and esteemed within a group, community, or environment. It hinges on the human emotional necessity to be a fundamental part of social systems in an environment where individuals feel safe, supported, and acknowledged for their uniqueness (Jenkins, 2025). In this research project, a sense of belonging was implied through the SEND learners' voice. Through semi-structured interviews, 80% of the participants voiced that they are comfortable in their current surroundings and feel that they are better placed in the specialist provision. After the participants had visualised their integration into mainstream settings, I asked them to state their intentions on whether they would like to remain in their current setting (specialist) or if they would like to make the transition into mainstream education, followed by what they would say to those enforcing the integration if given the opportunity:

“I would tell them I want to stay in my current setting as I know my way around and

I know the people, this is better for me.” (S1)

“I would rather stay where I am as I would like to continue to explore my current place more.” (S2)

“Stay where I am – I know people and I am comfortable here.” (S4)

“I want to stay where I am – moving somewhere else would make me feel anxious and stressed, I would not look forward to going to it.” (S5)

Belonging is a common value that is shared among many provisions in the UK, both in mainstream and specialised settings. From the perspective of mainstream education, having a sense of belonging is important for non-SEND learners, however, when we consider individuality among learners in mainstream settings, it is more difficult for a learner to comprehend how they contribute to upholding the values of the provision.

For instance, a mainstream learner in FE may have a 1 in 1200th chance of their achievements or contributions being celebrated, examples of these could include performing a solo session on a musical instrument or celebrating personal sporting achievements. In these circumstances, it is typically the 'stand-out' students that have these opportunities, whereas for less gifted non-SEND

learners, this is a rarity. In comparison, a SEND learner in a specialist FE provision of around 40 pupils are more likely to have their achievements recognised and celebrated as the pool is a lot smaller. In my experience as a SEND practitioner, numerous awards have been created in honour of alumni which are presented to individuals in specialised settings to celebrate their achievement, in some cases it has been the academic progress they have made over the duration of the year. Meanwhile, if this progress was replicated in a mainstream setting, it is likely that this would be recognised through moving the learner into a higher set in that subject area.

The qualities of a learner in a specialist provision contributes more effectively to their sense of belonging as opposed to how these qualities would be recognised in a mainstream setting. These qualities are recognised by the school community that supports them. This is reinforced by S1 and S4 where they highlighted that they “want to stay” because they “know the people, they feel comfortable, and this is better for them.” S5 reiterated that they “want to stay where they were”, scoping their feeling of anxiety, a theme that was discussed previously, but also add that they would feel “stressed”, and “would not look forward to going to the new setting.” Interestingly, the association of the transition to mainstream education triggered stress for S5 which reinforces a sense of comfort in their familiar surroundings. A robust sense of belonging in SEND education correlates with enhanced wellbeing and the attainment of personal outcomes. This is likely to be accomplished in specialised settings where intentional efforts are undertaken to cultivate supportive connections, promote inclusive practices, and establish situations in which every student feels accepted and appreciated (*Cullinane, 2021; Evans and Lynch, 2023; Pearce, 2023*).

6.4 - An atomistic approach

A holistic approach by practitioners is pivotal in SEND education as they must ensure that their understanding of their learners' needs is current, and that they are familiar with how their practice can best support SEND learners in fulfilling their potential, as well as ensuring that the learners feel safe and secure in the learning environment. In my findings, I found that a common concern shared by the teachers in the questionnaire was around how they envisaged mainstream educators struggling to implement the support required for the SEND learners. I asked the teachers to describe what it would look like if SEND learners were moved into mainstream education:

“Initially, it could be quite challenging for staff...SEND learners may not receive as much wrap-around support.” (T1)

“Mainstream teachers would struggle without a lot of training. SEND pupils would be marginalised, their needs would not be met, and their mental health would suffer. They would not receive enough support due to higher class sizes.” (T2)

“Integrating SEND learners into mainstream settings would require proper support, teacher training, and resources to be put in place. Without these, providers face issues such as overcrowded classrooms and unmet learning needs, impacting both SEND and non-SEND learners.” (T3)

Referring to common frameworks in which teachers are measured against as part of their role, both mainstream and SEND teachers are assessed against Teachers' Standards (England), both have appraisal objectives that are expected to be Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Time-bound (SMART) which are tailored to their role and experience (DfE, 2024; NEU, 2025). Both professionals also have SEND-specific expectations including personalisation and differentiation, use of Teaching Assistants (TA's), progress reviews, parent/carer engagement, and ongoing SEND training. However, the integration of SEND learners from specialist provisions into mainstream education would require a more robust approach from mainstream teachers as the cohort of learners are likely to have more complex needs. This does not imply that mainstream teachers lack the capability to adhere to this, however, the dilemma lies in the fact that it would be increasingly difficult to micro-assess SEND learners in a class size of twenty or more pupils. As stated, a holistic approach to supporting SEND learners is pivotal as this addresses the learner as a whole

which not only includes their academic or intellectual development, but also their emotional, social, ethical, physical and sometimes spiritual needs (*Pumpo, 2023*). From a professional perspective, assessing the academic and intellectual development of a class size around 15-20 learners is difficult enough, aligning this with the other responsibilities you have as a teacher such as high expectations and workload creates what is often described as a ‘burnout’ (*Schwab, 2024*). I find it immensely difficult to imagine the potential repercussions faced if mainstream teachers were not only tasked with being able to provide the holistic support needed to support SEND learners, but also finding the time to complete, understand and implement SEND-specific training to support SEND learners with complex needs.

Moreover, quantitative research has stated that almost forty thousand teachers left their profession in the 2021/2022 academic year, whilst almost a third of early career teachers (ECT’s) leave the profession within 5 years (*Henshaw, 2023; Booth, 2024*). Reasons for leaving the profession include high workloads, mental health and wellbeing, and pupil behaviour. In the context of integrating SEND learners into mainstream settings, an increased workload and teacher burnout could result in educators not being able to meet specific needs of SEND learners, potentially resulting in an increase in poor student behaviour and classroom management challenges, leading to more teachers leaving the profession (*Smithers and Robinson, 2003; Kenneally and Scotcher, 2022; Hoole, 2023*).

6.5 - The 'spiralling' gap

The 'spiralling' gap refers to the difference in academic and intellectual development that could be created between SEND learners and non-SEND learners if both groups attended mainstream education. It could be argued that this gap already exists taking into consideration the various curriculums that are followed depending on the type of learner accessing the education. For example, in a local authority maintained secondary school, students will follow the National Curriculum (NC). In a specialist secondary school provision, it is likely that students will follow adapted curriculums which are often broken down into separate levels that are appropriate for the learners accessing them, this normally entails a formal curriculum, an 'informal' curriculum, and a pre-formal curriculum. In a situation where SEND learners are integrated into mainstream educational settings, for provisions to be fully inclusive they would need to be flexible in being able to recruit teaching and learning staff that could fully support learners across each curriculum. However, when we consider 'inclusivity' and attempt to create an understanding of how this would look post-integration, it is difficult to imagine SEND learners with complex needs in the same classroom as those who are non-SEND, and this is not subject specific. If SEND learners were to integrate and were required to attend classes designed to meet their needs, an argument could be made that the provider is aiming to be fully 'inclusive', however, the question remains of whether this would be inclusion, or 'segregation'. If we assume that both SEND learners and non-SEND learners are in the same classroom, a 'spiralling' gap would be created. As part of the questionnaire, I posed the following question to teachers: 'In a mainstream setting, referring to learner's needs, do you feel that there are needs that could be met but are not yet met?' T2 responded with:

"It's been eight or nine years since I worked in a mainstream school. As a newly qualified teacher I felt that their needs were met. However, these were Year 3 pupils (aged 7-8 years), and they were not hugely behind their peers. I would argue that as they got older, this gap would widen significantly, and they would not be able to fully access the curriculum." (T2)

As an individual progresses beyond primary education, it is evident that learning intensifies due to expanding knowledge and vocabulary which is needed to show comprehension. Relating this to the academic and/or development goals of non-SEND or SEND learners who attend mainstream and specialist provisions, if we focus on the subject of English as an example, a non-SEND learner might be expected to write a structured story by the end of Year 8 (aged 12-13 years), whereas a

SEND learner with significant communication needs might explore storytelling through pictures, drama, or digital media, focusing on expressing preferences and making choices. The SEND learner would require tailored support through the means of a teacher or TA to support their communication needs in being able to meet their personal development goal. However, as stated, many teachers are burnout due to excessive workloads and high expectations, and neighbouring this with a low number of TA's in SE and FE provisions asserts that the needs of SEND learners could not be fully met in a post-integration world. T3 noted:

“Yes – support staff provided do not always possess SEND specialisms and are not able to fully support the needs of SEND learners.” (T3)

Ultimately, in a post-integration world, where provisions could not provide specialist learning and support for SEND learners, the unmet needs of these learners would create a gap between them and their non-SEND peers. The longer that this gap exists, and grows, it would eventually spiralise to an extent that could not be controlled, abandoning the growth and nurture which is essential to SEND learners in its wake.

6.6 – Lack of awareness

It could be argued that a lack of awareness derives from a range of figures involved in the process of ‘integrating or including’ SEND learners in mainstream settings. Referring to politics, it is debatable that the motivation behind integration or inclusion is financially driven:

“The motivation of government for putting SEND pupils into mainstream education is financial...the lasting damage to the mental health of children forced into a setting that they are not able to deal with will cost society way more. It's a false economy. Save a little now, but it will cost far more in the future.” (T2)

Studies demonstrate that educating students with SEND in mainstream settings is typically more cost-effective than in segregated special institutions. OECD research indicates that segregated placements can incur expenses seven to nine times greater, while per-capita expenditures for special education are around 2.5 times higher than those for mainstream education with adequate support (*European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2016*). Further studies suggest that schools in England have experienced substantial funding cuts for SEND provision since 2015, with a 17% reduction reported. Only 1% of school leaders believe they have sufficient funding to meet the needs of SEND pupils, and funding constraints are a major barrier to effective inclusion. These pressures can incentivise mainstream inclusion as a way to stretch limited resources further (*Warnes. Et Al., 2021; Demetriades, 2024*). *Demetriades (2024)* also notes that it is governmental statement and policy documents that highlight the goal of providing all learners (children), including those with SEND, access to high-quality education and participation in mainstream society. Therefore, it could be argued that the integration or inclusion of SEND learners in mainstream settings is financially motivated, yet it is also important to note that it is their policies and statements that contribute towards their motivation. However, it is questionable as to whether this is an independent effort as a nation, or whether it is the UK’s part in the collective effort of ensuring ‘equitable and quality access to education for all’ (*United Nations, 2022*).

A lack of awareness could allude to SEND learners not fully comprehending how their integration into mainstream settings would look. I posed the question of whether SEND learners should have a say on their integration into mainstream settings:

“I can’t think of many pupils who would understand the impact it would have. I have pupils who believe they should be in mainstream but are demonstrably ill-equipped to be there academically and socially.” (T2)

In my professional experience within SEND education, I know there is a great variation in the specific needs of learners. Without stereotyping, a range of SEMH learners that I have supported in specialist provisions struggle to comprehend why they are being educated in a specialist setting. In essence, mainstream provisions cannot cater for their needs because of the learners’ academic level, thus provoking situations where SEMH learners become dysregulated and pose challenging behaviours which impacts upon their peers and their educators. Drawing from experience, the learners I have worked with similar to that of what I have described believe that they attend specialist provision under the impression that mainstream provisions ‘could not control their behaviour.’ As SEND practitioners we have the responsibility of supporting SEND / SEMH learners to prepare for adulthood, to support them in being able to live independently and potentially work their way into employment. Therefore, integrating learners with this belief into mainstream settings where their needs are likely to be unmet will provide a dis-service to both the learner and the community in which they will inhabit in the future.

7. Evaluation

In this final part of the paper, I will provide an evaluation of the research where I will discuss whether the research aims were met. The main findings of the research will be summarised in this section, and I will also refer to any changes or improvements that would be made to the project if it were conducted again. I will make recommendations which will refer to further research, and what this should focus on, as well as summarising what I have learnt about my conduct of educational research, scoping strengths and areas for development.

7.1 - Has the research project met its aims?

The aim of this research was to add qualitative data using reflexive thematic analysis on the concept of integrating SEND learners into mainstream settings by exploring the perspectives of SEND learners and their practitioners. By using semi-structured interviews as a method to collect qualitative data from SEND learners, for the first time, their voices have been heard through using this research project as a medium. Moreover, the inclusion of exploring the perspectives of educational practitioners who work in SEND education has been paramount in this research. The data collected from the teachers' questionnaire has enlightened external stakeholders, such as those in governmental roles, to comprehend the challenges and implications that would accommodate the integration of SEND learners into mainstream education.

As stated, this project did not aim to provide a verdict of either SEND learners or their practitioners on the concept of integration of SEND learners into mainstream settings. The intention of this small-scaled research was to explore several perspectives with the hope that the findings would trigger interest in this topic, potentially progressing to a large-scale research project in the future.

Ultimately, taking into consideration the purpose of this research, I have collected and presented a range of perspectives from both SEND learners and SEND educators, therefore, I believe that the aims of this research project have been met.

7.2 – Main findings

The main findings in my research with SEND learners imply that the concept of integration into mainstream provisions creates a feeling of discomfort, which is highlighted through the theme of participants feeling anxious or nervous towards this. Considering the emotions of vulnerable individuals is both an ethical need and a practical requirement for ensuring decisions are equitable, courteous, and reduce harm. It safeguards their rights, cultivates trust, and results in more equal and effective outcomes (*McCullough, 2020*). Furthermore, the identified theme of SEND learners maintaining a sense of familiarity within their specialist provision enhances their sense of belonging. For SEND learners, a sense of belonging is not just beneficial-it is essential. It underpins their emotional wellbeing, academic achievement, social development, and full participation in education.

Several concerns are evident in the perspectives of SEND educators on the integration of SEND learners into mainstream educational settings according to the data presented in this research project. Taking into consideration how SEND learners would be supported in mainstream settings, it is manifested that SEND educators struggle to envisage how tailored support can be implemented in settings where practitioners do not specialise in this area, but noted the potential implications of doing so whereby SEND learners will not thrive and will become marginalised. In the absence of substantial enhancements in resources, staff training, inclusive practices, and school culture, SEND learners in mainstream education are at risk of marginalisation and failing to achieve their full potential (*WEDUC, 2022; DCProStaff, 2024*). It emerged that SEND educators anticipate a ‘spiralling’ gap in a post-integration world where the more vulnerable learners will fall considerably behind their non-SEND peers in most aspects of their development. This could then lead to further marginalisation for SEND learners where the gap would grow to an extent that is unmanageable. Furthermore, a lack of awareness from those in authoritative positions on the implications of integration was suggested by SEND practitioners in this research, highlighting that the concept of this is financially motivated. In contrast, it emerged that a misrepresentation of mainstream settings could be created by a range of SEND / SEMH learners who find it difficult to comprehend why they are educated in specialist provisions, noting that it is the belief of some learners that they should be educated in mainstream settings, but fail to realise that their needs would not be met in doing so.

7.3 - Changes / Improvements

Should I have the opportunity to conduct this research again, I would prioritise increasing the number of participants in the research as this would allow me to explore the perspectives of SEND learners and practitioners to a greater extent. Using large-scaled research to collect qualitative data provides further opportunities in identifying more themes that remain undiscovered and could prove invaluable to the concept of integrating SEND learners into mainstream educational settings. Large-scale research is typically more proficient at uncovering unrecognised themes owing to its wider scope, enhanced representativeness, and augmented statistical power. Nonetheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that although extensive research enhances the likelihood of uncovering new themes, it may occasionally lack the depth and contextual nuance found in smaller, qualitative investigations (*Ertl. Et Al., 2020; MacAuslan, 2018*).

7.4 - Recommendations

The main findings of my research suggest that the goal of ‘inclusion’ or ‘integration’ should be explored further. Initially, I believe that communication from the *United Nations (2022)* on how they envisage their members, including the UK, in achieving *SDG4* would provide stakeholders such as SEND learners and their practitioners further clarification on the matter. It is critical that learners’ voices are heard. The perspective of learners is not only valuable but fundamental in SEND education. It safeguards the rights of students, enhances educational offerings, empowers individuals, and cultivates a more inclusive and sincere educational atmosphere. Nonetheless, actualising its complete potential necessitates dedication, resources, and continuous endeavours to surmount obstacles to participation (*NUS, 2018*). Recognising the perspectives of SEND learners in their education acknowledges the ‘nothing about us without us’ fundamental tenet of the disability rights movement, who assert that individuals with disabilities must possess a significant role in influencing the policies, services, and societal frameworks that impact their existence (*Overdorff, 2020*). This resonates with SEND learners and their education, both presently and for those in the future.

Furthermore, the viewpoints of SEND practitioners are indispensable in the field of SEND education, and the potential ‘inclusion’ or ‘integration’ of SEND learners into mainstream provisions. SEND educators are the custodians in this field, they possess primary knowledge and experience in developing SEND learners to not only lead independent lives in adulthood but enable them to become valuable members of our communities.

The inclusion of SEND learners in mainstream settings should not be discouraged as an ambition, however, the findings of my research suggest that this idea should be explored further prior to its implementation. It is evident that the needs of some SEND learners can be met in mainstream settings as this is accomplished at present. Meanwhile, SEND learners with more complex needs are educated in specialist provisions as their needs cannot be met in mainstream settings. My question is, ‘How can we fully achieve ‘inclusive and equitable quality education for **all**’ where SEND learners with more complex needs must be educated in specialist provisions? When referring to **all** – could it be argued that we are still excluding those with more complex needs, and how do authorities intend on addressing this?’

In summary, my recommendations are that clarification is needed, further research should be conducted, and it is imperative that the voice of SEND learners is triumphant.

7.5 - Personal conduct of educational research

As a youthful researcher, my responsibilities as a data analyst have proven to be more intricate than expected. The decision I made to transcribe the interviews enabled me to thoroughly engage with and become acquainted with the data, identifying themes from the data collected from both SEND learners and practitioners proved initially challenging, but presenting the themes posed the greatest difficulty. As a professional who is passionate about SEND education, I advocate for those whose opinions are commonly dismissed. Through my experience, I anticipated themes that I would identify in my research, such as SEND learners feeling anxious towards the idea of mainstream integration and scoping the lack of governmental awareness where the teachers highlighted that the concept of inclusion is financially motivated. Axiology offers a framework for moral decision-making by concentrating on what is "good" or "valuable," including the choice to disseminate information that may benefit others. This value-oriented reasoning propels individuals beyond self-interest towards acts that benefit the wider society (*McGregor, 2012; Faulkner, 2024*). From the perspective of a researcher, the concern lay in my reluctance to share prevailing theories with those in authoritative positions, however, from an axiological perspective, it would be a disservice from me to SEND learners and fellow SEND educators to not share these findings.

From the onset, I acknowledged that conducting semi-structured interviews with SEND learners who struggle to articulate their feelings and opinions could only be accomplished with a strong mindset. This was reflected in the interviews which I conducted, I recognised that as a professional I felt obliged to support the learners in articulating their feelings, however, from a researching perspective I refrained from doing so to ensure that the qualitative data remained accurate. As a novice researcher, it emerged to me that neutrality in qualitative research signifies a dedication to ethical rigour rather than apathy. By prioritising participants' candid viewpoints, researchers maintain the integrity of their work while honouring the autonomy and dignity of everyone participating. Moral values may and ought to influence the contextualisation and application of findings, although they must not undermine the integrity of the data itself (*InnovateMR, 2024; McLeod, 2024*).

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9. Appendices

Appendix 1 – Google Forms - Questionnaire (SEND Teachers) Questions and responses

The screenshot shows a Google Form titled "SEND Teacher Survey". The form is in edit mode, with tabs for "Questions", "Responses" (3), and "Settings". The "Questions" tab is active. The form contains the following text:

SEND Teacher Survey

B I U ↻ ✕

This survey has been designed for SEND Teachers in order to collect data for a research project I am conducting as part of my Masters degree. The topic of this research is on the idea of integrating SEND learners into mainstream educational settings. You are not required to enter your name, or the organisation you work for as anonymity will be maintained for all participants throughout.

By submitting this form you are giving consent to the data being used and shared for research purposes. You do not need to provide your name or organisation's name to this form.

Describe what it would look like if SEND learners were moved into mainstream education? *

Long-answer text

Referring to SEND Education, what is your interpretation of inclusion as opposed to integration? *

Long-answer text

The form also includes a "Send" button in the top right corner and a "Total points: 0" indicator. A vertical toolbar on the right side of the form contains icons for adding, deleting, and duplicating questions, as well as a text tool.

Describe what it would look like if SEND learners were moved into mainstream education?

3 responses

Initially it could be quite challenging for staff and learners because lots of changes would need to be implemented to support the transition. It depends on how inclusive the provider wants the provision to be - I imagine it would depend on the individual learner as to whether they would need SEND provision within a mainstream setting, or if they could manage in a typical class. I think it would be quite difficult for SEND learners to move from a SEND provision into mainstream because it's very different, and could be a much bigger setting where they may not receive as much wrap-around support.

Mainstream teachers would struggle without a lot of training. The pupils themselves would be marginalised in schools, their needs would not be met and their mental health would suffer. They would not receive enough support due to higher class sizes.

Integrating SEND learners into mainstream education can promote inclusion and social integration but requires proper support, teacher training, and resources to be in place. Without these in place, providers face issues such as overcrowded classrooms and unmet learning needs, impacting both SEND and non-SEND students.

Referring to SEND Education, what is your interpretation of inclusion as opposed to integration?

3 responses

Integration means to move into something and I think for SEND education moving into mainstream this would not be an inclusive experience. I think this could result in an 'us and them' attitude from SEND learners

Referring to SEND Education, what is your interpretation of inclusion as opposed to integration?

3 responses

Integration means to move into something and I think for SEND education moving into mainstream this would not be an inclusive experience. I think this could result in an 'us and them' attitude from SEND learners because it would be such a huge adjustment. Inclusion for SEND education should be supportive, differentiated and fully capture the individual learner and their needs, whether this is in a SEND provision or mainstream.

Inclusion suggests that pupils would have the same opportunities as everyone else whilst taking account of individual needs. Integration suggests that they are shoehorned into an existing system that may, or may not, be suitable.

Inclusion is making positive changes to meet the needs of everyone involved. Integration is allowing a third party to join, but does not explicitly suggest change in the way inclusion does. Integration suggests that SEND learners need to just adapt to the mainstream ways.

What is unique about being a SEND Teacher? Why did you choose SEND education?

3 responses

I did not choose to specifically teach SEND education, it was something that was suggested by management because of my experience of different approaches and strategies of teaching. I have worked 1:1, small groups and with larger groups with the ability to adapt and contextualise learning based on the needs of the learners. I have worked with learners with very traumatic backgrounds, complex needs and

What is unique about being a SEND Teacher? Why did you choose SEND education?

3 responses

I did not choose to specifically teach SEND education, it was something that was suggested by management because of my experience of different approaches and strategies of teaching. I have worked 1:1, small groups and with larger groups with the ability to adapt and contextualise learning based on the needs of the learners. I have worked with learners with very traumatic backgrounds, complex needs and learners who have been removed from mainstream schools for behaviour, so I can recognise that some learners need a different approach. Teaching SEND is a unique teaching experience because no two sessions are the same. I think SEND teachers working with particularly vulnerable learners or those with complex needs have a lot more to think about when planning and delivering sessions to meet the needs of learners. In my experience with SEND there has been a lot more safeguarding concerns and issues to report also - this has resulted in extra meetings and extra paperwork, but extra stress too.

The occasional bizarre statements made by pupils are more prevalent and often hilarious. It forces me, as a teacher, to think of different ways of teaching a subject, since our pupils are often unpredictable in how they experience the world. I chose SEND education because I loved being on supply at my school. I'm not sure if I wouldn't switch back to mainstream if I left. I enjoyed both.

Being a SEND teacher is unique because it requires specialised skills, patience, and adaptability to support students with diverse needs. Too often, SEND learners are overlooked, and I chose SEND education to ensure every learner has the opportunity to thrive. Helping students exceed expectations and unlock new

If a mainstream teacher had concerns around integrating SEND learners into their classroom, what advice would you give them?

3 responses

If a mainstream teacher had concerns around integrating SEND learners into their classroom, what advice would you give them?

3 responses

I would tell them to ensure they have a strong understanding of the needs of the learners as a whole and identify strategies that would work for all learners to create a positive and inclusive learning environment. Expect some challenges whilst learners settle into their new class, but it's important to be patient whilst trying new techniques, strategies and approaches.

You need more training. Your school will have to provide it. If they don't, get in touch with your union representative.

It will be okay. Integrating SEND learners requires some flexibility for you to be able to create a supportive, inclusive classroom environment. Adapt your teaching methods, use assistive resources, and seek guidance from specialists to build your own confidence. Celebrate each student's unique progress and remember that small steps can lead to big achievements.

If you worked as a SEND Teacher in a mainstream setting, is it different to working as a SEND Teacher in a specialist setting? Explain your answer.

3 responses

I think it depends on how SEND looks in a mainstream setting. It also depends on the needs of the learner and whether it is in their interests to be in SEND or mainstream education. In a SEND specialist setting, the staff and learners are a bit more protected because they are in their own provision which is usually smaller

If you worked as a SEND Teacher in a mainstream setting, is it different to working as a SEND Teacher in a specialist setting? Explain your answer.

3 responses

I think it depends on how SEND looks in a mainstream setting. It also depends on the needs of the learner and whether it is in their interests to be in SEND or mainstream education. In a SEND specialist setting, the staff and learners are a bit more protected because they are in their own provision which is usually smaller than mainstream settings, they are familiar with staff and how to communicate; staff know the learners well and can accommodate the needs of the learners. In mainstream settings with their own SEND provision, this could also be said. In mainstream classrooms with learners with and without SEND, it takes thoughtful planning and delivery from the teachers and support staff, they may not have as much time to dedicate to a learner with SEND as they would if they were in a specialist provision.

I didn't.

The teaching and delivery remained unaffected as the classes were SEND-only, but the main college areas during break and lunch were shared with mainstream learners. From an inclusion perspective, it was positive to see many SEND students interacting and forming friendships with mainstream peers. However, there was also a risk that more vulnerable learners could be exploited or drawn into false friendships.

In a mainstream setting, referring to learners' needs, do you feel that there are needs that could be met but are not yet met? Explain your answer.

3 responses

In a mainstream setting, referring to learners' needs, do you feel that there are needs that could be met but are not yet met? Explain your answer.

3 responses

I think more specialised support for SEND in mainstream settings would be really useful, whether this is with specialised teachers or teaching assistants. I think CPD for staff would be helpful for ensuring all staff have a basic understanding of what SEND is and what it could or should look like in a mainstream setting.

It's been eight or nine years since I worked in a mainstream school. From what I remember, having just qualified, their needs were met. However, these were year 3 pupils and they were not hugely behind their peers. I would argue that as they got older, this gap would widen significantly and they would not be able to fully access the curriculum.

Yes- support staff provided do not always possess SEND specialisms and are not able to fully support the needs of SEND learners.

What is your experience with learner voice? Should SEND learners have a say on their integration into mainstream settings? Explain your answer.

3 responses

I think learners should be part of the conversation and have their opinions heard because it is so important for learners to have their say. I work with a learner with SEND and they have expressed that they feel 'weird' because they can't go to a 'normal school'. As a result of this, myself and another tutor try to make the

What is your experience with learner voice? Should SEND learners have a say on their integration into mainstream settings? Explain your answer.

3 responses

I think learners should be part of the conversation and have their opinions heard because it is so important for learners to have their say. I work with a learner with SEND and they have expressed that they feel 'weird' because they can't go to a 'normal school'. As a result of this, myself and another tutor try to make the learning feel as 'normal' as possible for this learner - delivery is in a venue of their choice and the theme of the content covered each week is their choice. This has been really important to ensure this learner continues to engage.

I can't think of that many pupils who would understand the impact it would have. I have pupils who believe they should be in mainstream, but are demonstrably ill equipped to be there academically and socially.

Support should always be person-centred, tailored to the individual needs, wishes, and goals of the learners. When appropriate, learners should contribute to their own EHCP, outlining their goals and aspirations. This should include plans for transitioning to a mainstream provider, highlighting how they would like to be supported during both the transition and integration process.

Summarise your opinion on the idea of integrating SEND learners into mainstream educational settings.

3 responses

I understand the importance of creating an inclusive learning environment for everyone, and I think this

Summarise your opinion on the idea of integrating SEND learners into mainstream educational settings.

3 responses

I understand the importance of creating an inclusive learning environment for everyone, and I think this could work well if more was done to support the transition for SEND learners into mainstream settings, but I also recognise that some learners need a specialist provision to thrive.

That depends on their needs. Some, with MLD, could be OK given the right support, but we are increasingly seeing pupils with SEMH issues. The motivation of government for putting SEND pupils into mainstream is financial. It will not benefit the children in any way. It could be argued that many of our pupils will not financially contribute to society in the future since, despite our efforts, they will never be able to get a job. However, the lasting damage to the mental health of children forced into a setting that they are not able to deal with will cost society way more. It's a false economy. Save a little now, but it will cost far more in the future.

I believe this approach is highly beneficial for higher-level SEND learners as they transition through education and into employment. For some, mainstream education provides their first experience of the 'real world,' exposing them to the challenges of a mainstream setting while still offering the safety and structure of an educational environment. For lower-level SEND learners, integration can help break down stigma surrounding SEND among non-SEND students and foster personal relationships. However, there are concerns that without the proper support, SEND learners may struggle to reach their full potential in this environment and may experience low levels of exploitation from other learners.

Responses from students - Interview

1. Can you tell me about what additional support you need as a student, and how you are supported in your current school / course?

S1 – ‘I need support with exams as I kind of get worked up when I’m in exams, and I get more help in my current setting than I did when I was in a mainstream school.’

S2 – ‘I get supported with my work in college like with Maths and English, and all of the other subjects I take as well, the staff already help me with these areas. I need support to read out the questions and ensure that I understand them properly.’

S3 – ‘Help with support – helped to understand things.’

S4 – ‘Help with work and understanding stuff.’

S5 – ‘Sometimes I am independent, but I may need help with what buses to get to the centre, sometimes I need help when needed.’

2. Can you tell me about how teachers meet your needs in your current setting?

S1 – ‘They explain things the way that I understand.’

S2 – ‘They basically are just there when I need to speak to them or when I need support from them.’

S3 – ‘Because they are a great help – good at explaining things, giving out instructions.’

S4 – ‘Yeah they help with work.’

S5 – ‘Teachers are helpful – If I don’t understand something they explain it to me to help.’

I want you to now imagine that you are going to change school / course. Your new place is not classed as 'specialist' and is described as 'typical'. **(Give example if needed)**. Imagine that you are going to meet lots of new teachers, and lots of new students.

3. Describe how you feel about what I have just told you.

S1 - 'Scared, how everyone would think of me, and if they would laugh at me, I would get worked up, and cry.'

S2 - 'A bit nervous and stuff, a bit wary about the place and stuff, meeting new people is a worry, obviously I will get to know them, but it is a new setting that is not familiar to me.'

S3 - 'Probably feel a bit nervous meeting new people.'

S4 - 'Feel good - feel alright'.

S5 - 'Probably make me feel a bit anxious, I wouldn't know what bus to get and would meet new tutors.'

S1 – ‘Give me worksheets of everything that they have on the board, give me homework to complete.’

S2 – ‘All of the same that I said before, when I need them, I would want them to be there for me and be able to help.’

S3 – ‘To help me fit in.’

S4 – ‘Feel good’.

S5 – ‘Help with reading.’

5. What new things are you looking forward to in this new place?

S1 – ‘Making friends, feeling like I would not want to be left out.’

S2 – ‘Different subjects and obviously making new friends and that.’

S3 – ‘Knowing what lessons I do, knowing the times of breaks and lunches.’

S4 – ‘Not much’.

S5 – ‘Making new friends.’

Is there anything you will miss about what you did before? Why?

S1 – ‘Yes, I would miss the teachers and how they help me with my learning.’

S2 – ‘No, I might miss certain tutors.’

S3 – ‘I miss seeing my old friends from here.’

S4 – ‘No.’

S5 – ‘Miss the staff – because I am used to them and have been here a while.’

What is this new classroom like?

S1 – ‘Really big with a lot of people in, this makes me feel scared.’

S2 – ‘Big, a lot of room, a lot more tables and chairs and that, and a big room like this.’

S3 – ‘It’s big and they have separate desks, one per student.’

S4 – ‘Similar to classroom now.’

S5 – ‘Class would look the same.’

Which other students are in your lesson?

S1 – ‘Noisy, kind of already in friendship groups.’

S2 – ‘They are my friends, and they have made me feel welcome in the class.’

S3 – ‘They seem friendly.’

S4 – ‘Nice.’

S5 – ‘Probably be nervous as well, shy as well – probably be helpful though and show people around.’

Why have you imagined it to be like this?

S1 – ‘Because I was used to big, overcrowded classrooms with lots of people.’

S2 – ‘Because I’m really open, really talkative and really friendly to other people.’

S3 – ‘Because I would like to fit in and make new friends, and I would like to be liked.’

S4 – ‘Don’t know.’

S5 – ‘Sometimes I try and make new people here feel welcome, being nice and kind and letting them have their space and letting them know that I will be there for them.’

6. If you had the option to go back in time to before you left to go to this new place, do you think you would tell them you want to go, or to stay where you are?

Explain your answer.

S1 – ‘I would tell them I want to stay in my current setting as I know my way around and I know the people, this is better for me.’

S2 – ‘I would rather stay where I am as I would like to continue to explore my current place more.’

S3 – ‘Stay in the new place – because I like going to new places and meeting new people.’

S4 – ‘Stay where I am – know people and I am comfortable here.’

S5 – ‘I want to stay where I am – moving somewhere else would make me feel anxious and stressed, I would not look forward to going to it.’

7. Going from your answer in Question 7, think about when you finish school / the course.

Are you better prepared for the future?

7. Going from your answer in Question 7, think about when you finish school / the course.

Are you better prepared for the future?

S1 – ‘A little bit’.

S2 – ‘No, I would rather stay on and pass my Maths and English which is my goal!’

S3 – ‘Yeah – I feel like I am ready to take a step forward.’

S4 – ‘Yeah.’

S5 – ‘Yeah.’

If you had chosen the other option, do you feel that you would respond with the same answer? Why?

S1 – ‘Not really, it would depend on if I would have been confident in the new setting.’

S2 – ‘Probably, I don’t know, I feel I would possibly be more prepared for the future, but I would like to explore the new setting more too.’

S3 – ‘I still feel the same – because I’ve been coming here for 3 years, I know what it is like.’

S4 – ‘Yes.’

S5 – ‘No, it takes quite a bit of time to settle in.’

Appendix 3 – Google Forms – Collated to Google Sheets (SEND Teachers & responses)

The screenshot shows a Google Sheet with the following data:

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Timestamp	Score	Describe what it would look like if SEND learn	Referring to SEND Education, what is your int	What is unique about being a SEND Teacher?	If a mainstream teacher had concerns around
2	19/02/2025 21:02:28		Mainstream teachers would struggle without a lot	Inclusion suggests that pupils would have the sar	The occasional bizarre statements made by pupil	You need more training. Your school will have to
3	25/02/2025 10:30:50		Integrating SEND learners into mainstream educa	Inclusion is making positive changes to meet the	Being a SEND teacher is unique because it requir	It will be okay. Integrating SEND learners require
4	27/02/2025 09:40:13		Initially it could be quite challenging for staff and	Integration means to move into something and it	I did not choose to specifically teach SEND educa	I would tell them to ensure they have a strong u
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